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Abstract:**Background:** Sleep disorders in adolescents are highly prevalent, with prevalence rates ranging from 25% to 40%. Sleep disorders include Dysomnias, Parasomnias and Circadian rhythm disturbances. The present study was undertaken with the purpose to analyse the sleep disorders among the adolescent population**Methodology:** This study was a cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey with adolescents with age range of 14 to 19 of both genders. Subjects with chronic illness or use of medication which are known to affect sleep were excluded from the study**Results:** Sleep disorders were observed in 27.8% of the adolescent study population. Among middle adolescents, the prevalence was 26.8%, compared to 30% among late adolescents. The study also found that 28.6% of adolescent males and 26.9% of adolescent females had sleep disorders. No statistical correlation was found between sleep disorders and age distribution or gender. However, mobile phone usage significantly impacted the occurrence of sleep disorders. Among the various sleep disorders, 19.1% of subjects reported nightmares, 18.8% reported restless leg syndrome, 17.1% experienced hypnagogic hallucinations, and 11.4% experienced hypnopompic hallucinations. Sleepwalking was observed in 0.4% of subjects, bruxism in 0.9%, and nocturnal enuresis in 0.1% of adolescents.**Conclusion:** Sleep disorders are not uncommon among adolescents, and these health issues should be addressed with increased awareness among both adolescents and their parents. Mobile phone usage significantly impacts the occurrence of sleep disorders. Therefore, adolescents need to be educated about the importance of adequate sleep, the components of good sleep hygiene, and strategies to facilitate healthy sleep behaviours.**Keywords:** sleep disorders, adolescent, mobile phone usage, Parasomnias.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The international Classification of sleep disorder categorizes sleep disorders as - Dysomnias, Circadian rhythm disturbances and Parasomnias [1]. The Dysomnias are disorders that produce either excessive sleepiness or difficulty in initiating or maintaining sleep. The Parasomnias result in disruption of sleep after it has been initiated.

In Circadian rhythm disturbance the routine over the whole of the 24-hour period may be shifted, including bedtime and sleep onset, naps, and meals. Teens may experience this problem as a result of physiological change in circadian rhythm [1]. Dysomnias can be Extrinsic dysomnias or Intrinsic. Extrinsic dysomnias develop as a result of influence outside the body (e.g. parental discipline, style, medication used): Intrinsic dysomnias are biologic based and include primary sleep disorders such as restless leg syndrome and obstructive sleep

apnoea [2]. Parasomnias are episodic in nature and are a reflection of central nervous system (CNS) immaturity. The Parasomnias result in disruption of sleep after it has been initiated. Parasomnias are characterized by abnormal polysomnography. Thus, they are more common in children than in adults and are generally outgrown with time. There is often a family history positive for these parasomnias.

As a group, these disorders are paroxysmal, predictable in their appearance in the sleep cycle, nonresponsive to environmental manipulation and characterized by retrograde amnesia. The diagnosis is often made by means of a thorough history [3]. Parasomnias includes Pavor Nocturnus or Night Terrors, Nocturnal Enuresis, Somnambulism and Somniloquy. Circadian rhythm disorder delayed sleep phase type (also known as delayed sleep

phase syndrome or DSPS) is most commonly seen in adolescents, although occasionally is also experienced by children [4]. The defining feature of DSPS is a sleep-wake schedule that is significantly and persistently delayed by 2 or more hours beyond the desired bedtime, and conflicts with an individuals activities of daily living (e.g. school, work, scheduled activities). Sleep disorders in adolescents are highly prevalent, with prevalence rates ranging from 25% to 40%, and they are often persistent [5]. The present study was undertaken with the purpose to analyse the sleep disorders among the adolescent population.

Methodology

This study was a cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey with adolescents (middle and late adolescent) with age range of 14 to 19 of both genders catering to middle and upper socioeconomic group. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses to all the questions. The subjects with physical illness like asthma, chronic sinusitis, recurrent abdominal pain, chronic back ache, seizure disorder, known cases of hypothyroidism, diabetes or any other chronic illness or use of medication which are known to affect sleep were excluded from the study.

The data was collected as per protocol and the results were tabulated using MS Excel and analysed using T-test, Chi square test.

Result and analysis-

The present study was undertaken with the purpose to analyse the sleep disorders among the adolescent population. Among all subjects participated in the study two third 665 (66.6%) were middle adolescent and one third 333 (33.4%) were late adolescents, and almost equal number of boys (56.2%) and Girls (43.8%) were studied. Male to Female ratio was 1.3:1. Among study population

sleep disorder was found in 278 (27.8%) of population. Among these 178 (64%) were middle adolescent and 100 (36%) were late adolescents. Among middle adolescent 26.8% had sleep disorders as compare to 30 % among late adolescents However, on statistical correlation was no significant association was found between age distribution and sleep disorders (p 0.577).

Among study population 56.4 % were males and 43.6.3% were females. Among males 28.6% and among females 26.9% had sleeping disorder. However, on statistical correlation there was no significant association between gender and sleep disorders was found in this dataset (p 0.585). Among study population 70.2% adolescents were mobile users.

Among mobile users sleep disorder was seen in 29.8% of adolescents in comparison to non-mobile users where it was seen in 23.2% of adolescents. When it was statistically correlated with sleeping disorder it was noticed that there is strong evidence to suggest that mobile phone usage significantly impacts the occurrence of sleep disorders (p 0.037). When prevalence of various sleep disorders was studied, in broader category of parasomnias 19.1% subjects reported nightmares, 17.1% report hypnogogic hallucinations and 11.4% hypnopompic hallucination, sleep waking was seen in (0.4%) subjects, bruxism (0.9%), and nocturnal enuresis (0.1%).

Among dysomnias, restless leg syndrome was reported in (18.8%) of subjects, narcolepsy in 3.8%, cataplexy 2.6%, Snoring (0.6%) and obstructive sleep apnoea (1.1%). Among Circadian rhythm disturbances 31.9% needed more than one reminder to get up in morning. 18.3% subjects felt tired and dragged during daytime. 3.3% subjects arrived late to class because of oversleep and 4% subjects reported falling asleep in morning classes.

Table 1: Age distribution and sleep disorder

Sleep Disorder	Middle Adolescents	Late Adolescents	Total	p value
Yes	178 (26.8%)	100 (30%)	278 (27.8%)	0.262
No	487 (73.2%)	233 (70%)	722 (72.2%)	
Total	665 (66.6%)	333 (33.4%)	998 (100%)	

Table 2: Gender distribution and sleep disorder

Sleep Disorder	Male	Female	Total	p value
Yes	161 (28.6%)	117 (26.9%)	278 (27.8%)	0.585
No	403 (71.4%)	319 (73.1%)	722 (72.2%)	
Total	563 (56.4%)	435 (43.6%)	998 (100%)	

Table 3: Mobile phone usage and sleep disorder

Sleep Disorder	Mobile User Yes	Mobile User No	Total	p value
Yes	209 (29.8%)	69 (23.2%)	278 (27.8%)	0.037
No	492 (72.2%)	228 (76.8%)	722 (72.2%)	
Total	701 (70.2%)	297 (29.8%)	998 (100%)	

Table 4: Distribution of sleep disorders reported by the study subjects

S.No.	Sleep Disorder	Total Subjects	No Problem	Frequent Problem	Infrequent Problem
Parasomnias					
1	Hypnogogic hallucination	945	612(64.8)	161(17.1)	172(18.2)
2	Hypnopompic hallucination	947	755(79.7)	108(11.4)	84(8.9)
3	Nightmare	948	626(66)	181(19.1)	141(14.8)
4	Sleep walking	971	931(95.9)	4(0.4)	36(3.7)
5	Bruxism	955	867(90.8)	9(0.9)	79(8.3)
6	Nocturnal enuresis	978	957(97.9)	1 (0.1)	20 (2.0)
Dysomnias					
7	Snoring	954	926(97.1)	6(0.6)	22(2.3)
8	Obstructive sleep apnoea	953	909(95.4)	11(1.1)	33(3.5)
9	Narcolepsy	945	826(87.4)	36(3.8)	83(8.8)
10	Cataplexy	948	885(93.4)	24(2.6)	39(4.1)
11	RLS	946	522(55.2)	189(18.8)	235(24.9)
Circadian rhythm disturbances					
12	Reminder to get up in the morning	977	523(53.5)	312(31.9)	142(14.5)
13	Overslept in the morning	977	868(88.8)	33(3.3)	77(7.8)
14	Fall asleep in the morning	978	845(86.4)	39(4)	94(9.6)
15	Feel Tired in the morning	976	568(58.2)	179(18.3)	229(23.5)
16	Reminder to get up in the morning	977	523(53.5)	312(31.9)	142(14.5)

Discussion

A total of 998 subjects participated in the study out of which two third 665 (66.6%) were middle adolescent and one third 333 (33.4%) were late adolescents, and almost equal number of boys (56.4%) and Girls (43.6%) were studied. This is similar to a study by Li Dan Lin et al where 51.7% boys and 48.3% girls were enrolled in China for similar study [6].

Among study population sleep disorder was found in 278 (27.8%) of population, which is similar to a systematic review and meta-analysis by Phiri Doreen et al which states the overall prevalence rate of sleep disturbance was 29% (95% CI: 0.201–0.403) [7]. However, in another study Li Dan Lin et al found it to be as high as 76.4% in rural China [6].

Among study population 665 (66.6%) were middle adolescent and 333 (33.4%) were late adolescents. Among middle adolescent 26.8% had sleep disorders as compare to 30% among late adolescents However, on statistical correlation was no significant association was found between age distribution and sleep disorders (p 0.262). This is similar to a study by Simsek Yasemin 2019 where he found no significant difference was noted in gender distribution, sleep duration, self-rated sleep quality and sleep quality between early, mid and late-adolescence groups [8].

Among study population 56.4 % were males and 43.6% were females. Among males 28.6% and among fe-males 26.9% had sleeping disorder. However, on statistical correlation there was no significant association between gender and sleep

disorders was found in this dataset (p 0.585). However in study by Sophie H Li et al found that girls had higher prevalence of sleep disorder and greater symptom severity [9].

Among study population 70.2% adolescents were mobile users. Among mobile users sleep disorder was seen in 29.8% of adolescents in comparison to non-mobile users where it was seen in 23.2% of adolescents. When it was correlated with sleeping disorder it was noticed that there is strong evidence to suggest that mobile phone usage significantly impacts the occurrence of sleep disorders (p 0.037). In a Systematic Literature Re-view by Sophia De Se et al also found that among adolescents there is a negative relationship between the use of electronic equipment, such as smartphones, and sleep, for reducing both the quality and quantity of sleep. There is also a relationship between nighttime smartphone use, insufficient sleep, and mental health problems [10].

When prevalence of various sleep disorders was studied, in broader category of parasomnias 19.1% subjects reported nightmares, 17.1% report hypnogogic hallucinations and 11.4% hypnopompic hallucination, sleep waking was seen in (0.4%) subjects, bruxism (0.9%), and nocturnal enuresis (0.1%). In Tucson Children's Assessment of Sleep Apnea (TuCASA) Study The incidence of enuresis (EN), sleep terrors (TR), sleep talking (ST) and sleep walking (SW) in these 10–18-year-old children was 0.3%, 0.6%, 6.0% and 1.1% respectively [11]. Among dysomnias, restless leg syndrome was reported in (18.8%) of subjects, narcolepsy in 3.8%, cataplexy 2.6%, Snoring (0.6%) and obstructive sleep apnoea (1.1%). In

other studies also it was noticed that obstructive sleep apnoea was present on 1-2 % of adolescents [12]. In another study by W Anuntaseree et al found 8.5% school going children snore and obstructive sleep apnoea was present in 0.69% students [13].

Among Circadian rhythm disturbances 31.9% needed more than one reminder to get up in morning. 18.3% subjects felt tired and dragged during daytime. 3.3% subjects arrived late to class because of oversleep and 4% subjects reported falling asleep in morning classes. This similar to prevalence noted in literature that Delayed sleep phase disorder (DSPD) — a circadian rhythm sleep disorder — is most commonly seen in adolescents with a prevalence of 7%–16% [14].

Conclusion

The present study highlights that sleep disorders are not uncommon among adolescents and should be addressed promptly. Raising awareness among adolescents and their parents about these health issues is essential. Additionally, mobile phone usage has a significant impact on the occurrence of sleep disorders. Therefore, adolescents need to be educated on the importance of adequate sleep, the components of good sleep hygiene, and strategies to promote healthy sleep behaviours.

Ethical approval - The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

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